

UPGRADING BIM PROCESSES IN A STRUCTURAL DESIGN OFFICE

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Supervisors

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Abstract

BIM software supports structural engineers in developing integrative allocation of structural design certification, reducing errors, and increasing the association between engineering and architecture departments. BIM allows structural engineers, detailers, and fabricators to improve structural design and association among professions. Even though much research discussed the importance of BIM processes in the structural engineering industry theoretically, there was a lack of research that discussed the implementation of BIM processes in practical aspects.

This work intends to provide practical upgrading for work processes in a Design office to deal with new BIM challenges and implementation for new BIM innovations to increase the work productivity for the desired BIM uses within a company in the Design stage. Also, define new strategies to re-engineer these processes to be more integrated and digitalized with controlling the production quality, increasing the work efficiency, and save more time.

Therefore, this dissertation has provided upgrading framework for the BIM process in the design stage to achieve the desired BIM uses for Newton design office through revising the internal BIM template with objects library and modify them to cover the design stage needs. Also, revise the used modelling and design processes and automate some repetitive tasks so designers can use their productive time more wisely.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2021-AlyAhmed-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/tSrrWW7mVfE>

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